

THE ISSUE OF IDEOLOGY IN FOREIGN LITERATURE

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7883442>

Annotatsiya: This article consists of opinions about the concept of ideology, as well as the history and origins of language ideology and its significance in foreign literature.

Key words: Ideology, Anthropology, Linguistic anthropology, Sociolinguistics, Assumptions, Fantasies, Aggregation, Legitimation, Universality, Promoter, Comprehensive guidance.

In our modern life, when thinking about the concept of language and several issues surrounding it, in particular, views on language ideology, the usage of it and its role in the life of society, it is appropriate to dwell mainly on ideological issues in foreign literature. If we turn our attention to the history of language ideology, a lot of information about it will be more detailed for us. "Language ideology is, within anthropology (especially linguistic anthropology), sociolinguistics, and cross-cultural studies, any set of beliefs about languages as they are used in their social worlds. Language ideologies are conceptualizations about languages, speakers, and discursive practices. Like other kinds of ideologies, language ideologies are influenced by political and moral interests and they are shaped in a cultural setting. When recognized and explored language ideologies expose how the speakers' linguistic beliefs are linked to the broader social and cultural systems to which they belong, illustrating how the systems beget such beliefs. By doing so, language ideologies link implicit and explicit assumptions about a language or language in general to their social experience as well as their political and economic interests" [1] Ideology in foreign literature, in general, the concept of ideology is considered as a set of interests, values and ideas belonging to a certain nation or society. The ideology is the set of views or beliefs of a group of people or a person. Accordingly, it can be said that every person and society have its own ideology. "Ideologies are not merely fantasies or aggregations of tendentious lies. Indeed, they may in some instances, constitute the most enlightened and perceptive understanding of human thought and action then attainable: this is possible because ideologies are always generated by social reality. They are not, however, simply straightforward reflections of reality, but partial and incomplete attempts to apprehend and explain reality. Thus, an ideology mediates between actual human practices and understanding of the nature of those practices. It is in the process of trying to perceive, interpret and represent reality that distortion occurs, sometimes unwittingly and sometimes as a result of prior intention. As ideologies play a dynamic role in the relations between human beings, they are usually susceptible to revision and development, according to changing social conditions. However, the need to fulfil particular functions ensures that ideologies typically share some constant features. For example, overtly political ideologies offer some explanation of the past and present, a blueprint for the future, and a statement of the goals and values deemed important by the promoters of the ideology. Such ideologies typically provide more or less comprehensive guidance for action and seek to draw support and legitimation from all or most members of a given society. In this way, political ideologues and activists try to establish the universality of their own perspectives. The manner in which ideologies are created and transmitted will obviously vary according to the general conditions pertaining to a given society" [2].

It is known that the history of language ideology in general goes back a long way."Some historians of philosophy have called the 19th century the age of ideology, not because the word itself was then so widely used, but because so much of the thought of the time can be distinguished from that prevailing in the previous centuries by features that would now be called ideological. Even so, there is a limit to the extent to which one can speak today of an agreed use of the word. The subject of ideology is a controversial one, and it is arguable that at least some part of this controversy derives from disagreement as to the definition of the word ideology. One can, however, discern both a strict and a loose way of using it. In the loose sense of the word, ideology may mean any kind of action-oriented theory or any attempt to approach politics in the light of a system of ideas. Ideology in the stricter sense stays fairly close to Destutt de Tracy's original conception and may be identified by five characteristics: (1) it contains an explanatory theory of a more or less comprehensive kind about human experience and the external world; (2) it sets out a program, in generalized and abstract terms, of social and political organization; (3) it conceives the realization of this program as entailing a struggle; (4) it seeks not merely to persuade but to recruit loyal adherents, demanding what is sometimes called commitment; (5) it addresses a wide public but may tend to confer some special role of leadership on intellectuals

Ideologies, in fact, are sometimes spoken of as if they belonged to the same logical category as religions. Both are assuredly in a certain sense "total" systems, concerned at the same time with questions of truth and questions of conduct, but the differences between ideologies and religions are perhaps more important than the similarities. A religious theory of reality is constructed in terms of a divine order and is seldom, like that of the ideologist, centred on this world alone. A religion may present a vision of a just society, but it cannot easily have a practical political program. The emphasis of religion is on faith and worship; its appeal is to inwardness and its aim the redemption or purification of the human spirit. An ideology speaks to the group, the nation, or the class. Some religions acknowledge their debt to revelation, whereas ideology always believes, however mistakenly, that it lives by reason alone. Both, it may be said, demand commitment, but it may be doubted whether commitment has ever been a marked feature of those religions into which a believer is inducted in infancy. Even so, it is in certain religious movements that the first ideological elements in the modern world can be seen.

Seventeenth-century England occupies an important place in the history of ideology. Although there were then no fully fledged ideologies in the strict sense of the term, political theory, like politics itself, began to acquire certain ideological characteristics. The swift movement of revolutionary forces throughout the 17th century created a demand for theories to explain and justify the radical action that was often taken. Locke's *Two Treatises of Government* (1690) is an outstanding example of literature written to justify individual rights against absolutism. This growth of abstract theory in the 17th century, this increasing tendency to construct systems and discuss politics in terms of principles, marks the emergence of the ideological style. In political conversation generally it was accompanied by a growing use of concepts such as right and liberty—ideals in terms of which actual policies were judged" [3].

We all know that everything has its good and bad side. Also, ideologies can be both positive and negative. Some of them call for positive changes in people, while others, with different

ideologies and ideas, make people prone to disagreements and conflicts. It is probable that every person can have a positive ideology with their pure and creative ideas.

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